

Farming systems

Raising grass carp with deepwater rice

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We experimented with raising grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella* Val) along with deepwater rice NC492 at two sites during 1988 wet season. Rice seedlings were transplanted 4 Jul 1988 at Girirchalk (Midnapore district) and 20 Jul 1988 at Gosaba (South 24-Parganas district). Fish fingerlings were stocked 1 mo later; average length and weight at stocking were 8.0 cm and 12.1 g at Girirchalk and 10 cm and 18.4 g at Gosaba. No fish feed and no

Production of rice and fish under integrated deepwater rice + grass carp culture trial. West Bengal, India, 1988 wet season.

Experimental site	Experimental plot								Fish yield (kg/ha)
	Control -only deepwater rice (yield in t/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)	Fish stocked (1 fish/m ²)	Stocking		At harvest		Recovery (%)	
				Length (cm)	Wt (g)	Length (cm)	Wt (g)		
Girirchalk (Midnapore)	1.5	1.8	600	8.0	12.1	15.2	80.0	54.0	432.0
Gosaba (24 Parganas S.)	1.8	1.9	320	10.0	18.4	19.2	96.5	60.0	575.8

fertilizer was applied.

Rice stand count (recorded from a 0.5- × 0.5-m wooden frame) and general field observations were taken periodically. The fish culture period was 120 ± 10 d.

Rice yield data were taken by standard crop-cut method, adjusted to 14% moisture. Fish growth was measured and yield computed.

Stem density did not differ in plots with grass carp and those without fish. Submersed aquatic weed density appeared to be less in plots with fish. Production of rice and grass carp are summarized in the table.

The results indicate that grass carp may be incorporated into a deepwater rice - fish system without jeopardizing rice cultivation. □

Farm machinery

A hand-operated rice huller

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A hand-operated rice huller has been developed that is inexpensive, simple to construct, and easy to maintain. Its two main components are a commercial hand mill and a conversion kit to replace the stationary disk with a gum rubber disk (see figure). When the abrasive rotating disk is turned, rice grains are pressed against the rubber disk and rolled out. The soft rubber disk removes the hulls with minimal damage to the kernels. The huller can also be used for millet and spelt wheat.

The mill will hull 12 kg short grain rice/h. □

Hand-operated rice huller can process 12 kg rice/h.

Postharvest technology

Aflatoxins in stored rice

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Mycotoxin contamination of agricultural commodities and the consequent health hazards are problems of considerable relevance in tropical countries. Aflatoxins are the most potent hepatotoxic and carcinogenic agents. In staples such as rice, aflatoxins are of great significance to human health.

Rice can become contaminated with aflatoxin under high moisture conditions that may occur with improper storage, insect infestation, or high humidity.

Studies in India indicate that, under normal circumstances, aflatoxin contamination of rice is low (Table 1). However, rice exposed to stress conditions (such as heavy rains) can become highly susceptible to fungal invasion and increased aflatoxin contamination. In rice damaged by

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific understanding.
